

Attempts to fine-tune the Segment Anything Model for instance segmentation of fluorescent microscopy images of *Bacillus subtilis*

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Abstract. Recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) have propelled significant innovations across various scientific fields, particularly in the biological sciences, where AI’s application in image segmentation tasks has dramatically improved research efficiency. Specifically, the utility of AI in generating instance segmentation masks from microscopy images has become an area of keen interest due to its potential to streamline cell population quantification processes. This study addresses the challenge of fine-tuning an existing AI model, the Segment Anything Model (SAM) developed by Meta, for enhanced instance segmentation of fluorescent microscopy images of *B. subtilis*, a model organism frequently used in microbial research. The primary objective of this research is to optimize the SAM model’s performance for the specific task of segmenting *B. subtilis* cells, aiming to simplify cell counting tasks for researchers. Here, we show that our attempts to fine-tune SAM specifically for *B. subtilis* segmentation encountered significant challenges, leading to unexpected outcomes in model performance. Our findings indicate that fine-tuning SAM for this specialized application did not achieve the anticipated improvements. Instead, the model exhibited tendencies for over-segmentation, highlighting the complexities involved in adapting generalized models to specific imaging tasks. This contrasts with prior successes in broadly applied segmentation models, suggesting a need for further investigation into fine-tuning methodologies and model adaptability. The results of this study underscore the intricacies of applying AI to highly specialized imaging tasks. Our work contributes to the ongoing dialogue on the potential and limitations of AI in biological imaging, emphasizing the necessity of tailored approaches for specific research needs.

1 Introduction

The recent publicity of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has marked a new era in the landscape of scientific research, characterized by their expanding capabilities and diverse applications. These technologies have transcended the traditional boundaries of Information Technology, making significant advances in various scientific fields, notably within the biological sciences. Especially for image segmentation tasks like cell segmentation for population quantification the application of AI can significantly reduce the time needed for the population assessment and thus increase velocity of new research.

This paper focuses on exploring the possibilities and effectiveness of adapting an existing segmentation model for the purpose of generating instance segmentation masks from fluorescent microscopy images of *B. subtilis*. The model in question is the Segment Anything Model (SAM), developed by Meta [5], chosen for its adaptability and comprehensive architecture.

1.1 Transformer Models

Transformer models have emerged as a groundbreaking development in the realm of artificial neural networks. These models are adept at understanding the context within various types of data, including text and images. Introduced by the seminal work "Attention Is All You Need" by Google researchers [10], transformer models leverage attention mechanisms to learn complex data relationships. This innovative approach enables neural networks to grasp intricate patterns in data without relying on extensive labeled datasets, marking a significant leap forward in machine learning techniques.

1.2 Segment Anything

SAM, a creation of Meta Research [5], shows the application of transformer technology in image segmentation. Built upon the foundation of the Visual Transformer (ViT) model by Google Research [1], SAM incorporates a tripartite structure: a vision encoder, a prompt encoder, and a mask decoder. This structure facilitates a comprehensive processing pipeline where the vision encoder, based on the ViT transformer, generates embeddings for input images. As a model that can be prompted, SAM includes a prompt encoder for generating embeddings for various types of prompts: points, boxes, and text. However, it is noteworthy that while points and box prompts are supported in the public release of SAM, text prompts remain unavailable. The mask decoder then utilizes the embeddings from the image and prompt encoders to predict masks, reflecting the input. SAM's training involved over 1 billion masks across more than 11 million images, illustrating its extensive learning and adaptability capabilities.

2 Related Work and Motivation

This study draws considerable inspiration from the significant contributions of two foundational papers, MedSAM and CellSAM, which explore the nuanced application of SAM tailored to specific imaging contexts to achieve enhanced performance over generalized model applications. The focus on medical and cellular image segmentation by these works highlights the challenges and limitations encountered when employing generalized models for specialized image types.

2.1 MedSAM

MedSAM [6] represents a pioneering approach in the field of medical image segmentation, utilizing a vast dataset comprising over one million images. This comprehensive dataset enables the model to achieve unparalleled performance across a wide spectrum of segmentation tasks, outperforming existing task-specific models in terms of generality and efficiency. MedSAM's ability to extract biomarkers with exceptional accuracy [6] for tumor quantification showcases its potential in revolutionizing diagnostic methodologies and facilitating personalized treatment plans. The model's success can be attributed to its foundation on a diverse and extensive dataset, offering a versatile and adaptable solution for medical imaging analysis.

2.2 CellSAM

In the realm of cellular image segmentation, CellSAM [4] introduces an innovative adaptation of the Segment Anything Model, incorporating a novel prompt engineering technique for mask generation. This model integrates an automatic cell detection mechanism, CellFinder, enhancing its capability to accurately segment cells across a variety of cellular imaging datasets. These datasets span mammalian cells, yeast, and bacteria, encompassing different imaging modalities. The resultant performance of CellSAM stands at the forefront of the field, demonstrating the efficacy of tailored model adjustments in addressing the complexities of cellular image segmentation.

2.3 Motivation

The exceptional outcomes achieved by MedSAM and CellSAM serve as the foundation for this work’s motivation. The objective is to fine-tune a model on a more constrained dataset, thereby simplifying the task of cell counting for researchers at the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology in Plön. While both MedSAM and CellSAM leverage extensive datasets for their foundational models, this work aims to focus on a more use-case-specific model, particularly for the segmentation of fluorescent microscopy images of *B. subtilis*. This approach represents a departure from the foundational model strategy, emphasizing the development of a specialized model tailored to meet the unique requirements of the specified use case.

3 Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology employed for the fine-tuning process, drawing on the foundational work established by the developers of MedSAM and CellSAM. The approach is detailed in two primary sections: Dataset Preparation and Fine-Tuning Implementation.

3.1 Dataset Preparation

The foundation of any artificial intelligence training or fine-tuning initiative is the compilation of a robust training set. In this case, the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology in Plön contributed a series of fluorescent microscopy images of *B. subtilis*. This dataset comprised 100 high-resolution images (2048x2048 pixels), provided as a single OME-TIFF file. Each image incorporated three channels, capturing the raw data from the camera sensor. Initially, the dataset was segmented into 100 individual images to facilitate the selection of a subset for detailed labeling. The first 13 images were chosen for this purpose. Labeling was conducted using QuPath, a bioimaging analysis software, supplemented by manual input via a tablet. This process involved outlining the cell perimeters within the images. Subsequent to the tracing, QuPath’s functionality was utilized to fill any gaps in the cell masks. A script for QuPath, sourced from GitHub [11], enabled the export of these masks into image files. To prepare the dataset for loading into the SAM model, both the masks and the corresponding images were divided into 64 patches, each measuring 256x256 pixels. This was necessary because SAM is unable to process images at their original size. The dataset was further augmented through a series of rotations, each patch being rotated three times by 90 degrees, effectively quadrupling the size of the dataset. This resulted in a total of 3328 patches, stored as a 3D-Array column within an Apache Arrow [3] table.

3.2 Fine-Tuning Code Implementation

The fine-tuning code was developed based on an exemplary Jupyter Notebook provided by Niels Rogge [8], tailored to suit the specific requirements of this project. The fine-tuning process was divided into three distinct phases: data loading, image preprocessing, and fine-tuning of SAM. The data loader’s primary function is to import the dataset for fine-tuning and to ensure the random shuffling of patches in each training epoch, preventing the model from learning the sequence of the data. The image preprocessor prepares the patches for fine-tuning, specifically by disabling RGB conversion, image resizing and rescaling, thus preserving the integrity of the original raw data captured in the OME-TIFF files. For the fine-tuning process, the AdamW optimizer was utilized, configured with a learning rate of 10^{-8} and a weight decay of 10^{-4} . The DiceCELoss function from the Monai Python library calculated the loss for each epoch. The fine-tuning was executed with a batch size of 15 over 10 epochs to evaluate improvements in image segmentation accuracy.

4 Results

The process of fine-tuning an existing segmentation model, specifically aimed at enhancing its capability to segment *B. subtilis* cells in fluorescent microscopy images, faced significant challenges. Despite the success of foundational models such as MedSAM and CellSAM in the field, our attempts to adapt a similar approach for a more specialized training set did not yield comparable results. Notably, even a minimal training duration of ten epochs led to a decline in the model’s performance in terms of image segmentation accuracy as seen in figure 1. Our observations indicated

Fig. 1: Binary segmentation masks before and after fine-tuning SAM with our dataset. Even without fine-tuning we see in 1a in the second row, fourth patch from the left has dotted artifacts which become worse with fine-tuning. Dark violet represent a zero and yellow a one in the binary segmentation mask. Even with minimal fine-tuning a massive over segmentation starts to occur.

a tendency for the model to over-segment images, frequently resulting in segmented patterns that manifested as dotted artifacts as seen in figure 1b. While these artifacts also existed with native SAM as seen in figure 1a, it got worse with fine-tuning. This phenomenon was not limited to the evaluation on a validation image set, as it was equally prevalent when inference was conducted on the training dataset itself. Such outcomes were anticipated, given the consistently high loss values recorded during training sessions as seen in figure 2. Efforts to rectify these high loss values and enhance model performance through various adjustments including learning rate and weigh-decay modification, batch-size adjustments, training set size alterations, and an increase in GPU power failed to produce any notable improvements.

The objective behind this study was not to develop a foundational model like MedSAM or CellSAM, but rather to fine-tune a segmentation model specifically for the precise task of segmenting *B. subtilis* cells in microscopy imagery. Despite the innovative approach and the specificity of the goal, the results fell short of expectations, underscoring the complexities and challenges inherent in fine-tuning segmentation models for highly specialized applications.

Fig. 2: Development of mean loss over fine-tuning epochs. Loss was calculated using DiceCELoss from the Monai Python library.

5 Discussion

This chapter delves into the outcomes of the attempt to fine-tune SAM, specifically aimed at improving its performance in segmenting *B. subtilis* cells in fluorescent microscopy images. Contrary to initial expectations, the fine-tuning process did not yield the anticipated enhancement in the model’s segmentation capabilities. This outcome prompts a critical evaluation of the fine-tuning methodology employed, alongside considerations for potential adjustments to optimize future attempts.

A key aspect under consideration is the application of a learning-rate optimizer [7] to identify an optimal learning rate coefficient. CellSAM for example, utilized a learning rate of 10^{-4} , a value that proved excessively high for our purposes, leading to rapidly escalating loss rates with each epoch. Although manual adjustments to the learning rate were made, the absence of a dedicated learning rate optimizer likely hampered the fine-tuning efficiency. This insight suggests that incorporating such an optimizer could significantly refine the learning rate selection process, potentially stabilizing and improving model performance. Additionally to learning-rate, optimizing other hyperparameters like weight-decay could also improve the results.

The size and diversity of the training dataset represent another critical factor in the fine-tuning process. Despite utilizing over 3,000 image patches, the dataset’s scale and variety may fall short when compared to projects like MedSAM, which incorporate millions of images [6]. This discrepancy raises questions about the sufficiency of our dataset for the task of fine-tuning a model for highly specific segmentation tasks. Expanding the dataset could, therefore, be a viable strategy for enhancing the model’s ability to generalize across a broader range of images, ultimately improving segmentation outcomes.

Batch size during training is also identified as a potential area for adjustment as MedSAM for example used a batch size of 160 [6]. Our fine-tuning attempt was performed with a batch size of 15 as this was the most the GPU memory could fit. Increasing the batch size could lead to more stable results through fewer parameter adjustments during training [9].

Lastly, the strategy for prompting the model is scrutinized. Unlike the CellSAM project, which employs the CellFinder model to generate precise bounding boxes for individual cells [4], our approach utilized a generalized bounding box encompassing the entire image patch. This simplification might have compromised the model’s segmentation precision, suggesting that a more sophisticated prompting mechanism could yield better segmentation results.

In summary, we identified the following potential sources of errors in our attempt to fine-tune SAM: learning rate and hyper parameter optimization, dataset size and diversity, batch size limitations, and prompting strategies. Each of these factors offers a distinct avenue for improvement, underscoring the complexity of fine-tuning segmentation models and the need for a multifaceted approach to enhance their performance. Future work will focus on addressing these issues, with the aim of achieving more accurate and reliable segmentation outcomes for fluorescent microscopy images of *B. subtilis* cells. To ascertain the primary contributors among these potential sources of error, a methodical strategy may be employed. This involves sequentially adjusting individual parameters to determine their impact on aligning results more closely with the desired outcome. Upon identifying the main sources of error, a composite strategy, involving the simultaneous adjustment of multiple parameters, can be adopted to enhance performance further.

6 Conclusion

The attempt to fine-tune SAM for segmenting *B. subtilis* cells in fluorescent microscopy images unveiled significant challenges, underscoring the complexities of tailoring advanced segmentation models to highly specialized applications. Despite the innovative approach and the specificity of the task, the results fell short of expectations, highlighting the necessity of a multifaceted strategy to enhance model performance. Future work will address identified issues such as learning rate optimization, dataset size and diversity, batch size limitations, and prompting strategies, aiming for more accurate and reliable segmentation outcomes. This study emphasizes the importance of continuous exploration and adaptation within the field of AI-driven biological image analysis, contributing valuable insights for future research endeavors.

Code and Data Availability

The code developed for the fine-tuning of SAM has been made publicly accessible on [GitHub](#). Correspondingly, the curated dataset associated with this publication can be found on [Zenodo \[2\]](#). This dataset encompasses ground truth data and labels, pre-segmented into patches and augmented through rotation to enhance variety. It is available in the Apache Arrow format, ensuring compatibility with the Python "datasets" library for ease of use.

Acknowledgements

This work would not have been possible without the invaluable resources and support generously provided by various individuals and institutions. Foremost, I extend my deepest gratitude to the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology in Plön for making the critical dataset available, which served as the backbone for this research. The accessibility of these data significantly propelled our research efforts, enabling a depth of analysis that was pivotal to our findings.

I would also like to extend a special thanks to Dr. Carsten Fortmann-Grote, whose expertise, patience, and dedication played a crucial role in navigating the complexities of the dataset. Carsten's insights and suggestions were not only instrumental in the data analysis phase but also enriched the overall quality of this study. The willingness to go above and beyond in assisting our research team reflects the exemplary commitment to advancing scientific knowledge.

Furthermore, my sincere appreciation goes to Professor Sören Werth, who has been a guiding light throughout this journey. Professor Werth's profound knowledge, constructive criticism, and unwavering support were key in the writing and development of this paper. The mentorship provided by Professor Werth has been invaluable, not only in shaping this research but also in my personal growth as a scholar.

This acknowledgment would be incomplete without mentioning all those who, directly or indirectly, contributed to the success of this research. I am deeply thankful for their collective efforts and contributions.

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